

**FORMATION OF A SPORTS FACILITIES MANAGEMENT SYSTEM IN
UZBEKISTAN**

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6483165>

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1st year of master's degree

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Abstract: *The article presents sports facilities such as sports schools, sports facilities, etc. The problems of the development of the management system of sports buildings are studied.*

Keywords: *sports facilities, financial resources, technical management, infrastructure management, commercial management.*

In modern Uzbekistan, a significant part of socially oriented branches of the national economy are experiencing serious difficulties in budget financing, despite the programs adopted at the regional level to support and develop this sphere. This is due to the previously existing residual principle of financing, as well as ill-conceived, ineffective reforms that significantly reduced the resource capabilities and potential of regional complexes.

The sports sphere is no exception in this regard, and moreover, the transition to the regional principle of sports management has further aggravated this problem. Today, each region is ready to determine the main directions of its sports policy, the amount of funding, based on local conditions, traditions, the availability of sports infrastructure, its technical equipment, the prevailing form of ownership. Despite the significant strengthening of the financial base of many regional sports organizations in recent years, the main funds still come mainly from budgets of various levels, and less from patrons and sponsors, even though the latter finance sports out of personal ambitions or even altruistic motives, not hoping to get anything in return.

This situation is very risky for regional sports, as with the rationalization of management at all levels, the validity of spending financial resources will be controlled more and more tightly.

In this regard, the issues of optimal management of sports infrastructure, reduction of utility costs and other costs for the maintenance and operation of sports facilities, especially for single-industry towns in depressed regions of Uzbekistan, seem to be quite relevant.

Technical management combines the work and services required to maintain and operate construction and technical systems and devices according to energy efficiency criteria.

Infrastructure management includes a full list of secondary services that improve the quality use of the property for its users.

Commercial management is the work and services from the previous two directions, which can be used to extract additional profit from the rental of temporarily vacant volumes and areas of a real estate object.

The main components of the sports infrastructure of the republic are sports schools, sports buildings and structures, their technical condition, etc., and the main indicators of its development are the provision of sports facilities to the population, one-time capacity, the amount of allocated budget funds, extra-budgetary sources of financing.

Among citizens of all categories and ages engaged in sports sections in physical education and sports organizations, the most popular sports are: mini-football, hockey, basketball, swimming, athletics, volleyball.

The problems of the building's infrastructure were the management of the catering system (the lack of the possibility of catering staff and visitors, especially in the evening), security management (an inefficient system for monitoring the entry and exit of users), cleaning management (involving a cleaning company on the principles of outsourcing), parking management (organization of parking spaces in the adjacent territory), the introduction of electronic document management. The solution of the above problems gives an indirect economic effect – reduction of non-productive time losses by the pool staff and visitors.

In the commercial management of the building, one main drawback was highlighted – inefficient use of premises. The following measures were proposed and implemented: area management through the information model of the building, which made it possible to use specialized premises more efficiently, for example, dry swimming and gymnastics halls); the introduction of a flexible pricing model for services provided increased the load of the sports facility in the most problematic daytime (from 11 to 14 hours).

In conclusion, we can give a solution to these problems. It is necessary to solve problems effectively. People need to understand what they are used for and most importantly, it is necessary to solve the problem with finance.

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